

Evaluation of diuretic effect and phytochemical screening of Agoho (Casuarina equisetifolia Linn., Family: Casuarinaceae) bark on male Sprague Dawley rats

Nathan Fater Mbayev*, Antso A. Samuel, Ezekiel Shiekuma Ater, Cyrine B. Pavo, Mary Claire Rafol, Anthony R. Marin
Pharmacy Department, School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines
*Corresponding author

Abstract

This study determined how the bark of Casuarina equisetifolia (Agoho) works as a diuretic towards male Sprague-Dawley rats. Two types of extracts from the bark—ethanolic and aqueous—were used with a cold maceration method and screened for phytochemicals. Sixteen male rats were divided into four groups: furosemide (positive control), saline solution (negative control), ethanolic extract, and aqueous extract. They measured the amount of urine each rat produced, along with the excretion of certain electrolytes such as sodium, potassium, and chloride for three hours. Results showed that both extracts increased urine production compared to the control groups. While the ethanolic extract was more effective than the aqueous one, furosemide remains the most potent control. Phytochemical screening found different compounds such as flavonoids, alkaloids, and tannins, which are linked to diuretic effects. The study suggests that extracts from Agoho bark have some diuretic qualities and support their use in traditional medicine. More research, including human studies and medical investigations, is needed to better understand their full potential as treatment.

Keywords: Diuretics; Agoho; Furosemide; Ethanolic extract; Aqueous extract.

To cite this article:

Mbayev, N. F., Samuel, A. A., Ater, E. S., Pavo, C. B., Rafol, M. C., & Marin, A. R. (2022). Evaluation of diuretic effect and phytochemical screening of Agoho (Casuarina equisetifolia Linn., Family: Casuarinaceae) bark on male Sprague Dawley rats. *The Capsule*, 3, 19-27.

Introduction

Diuretics, also called water pills, are medicines that help the body get rid of more water and salt through urine. These medicines reduce the amount of fluid in blood vessels, which helps lower blood pressure. Diuretics are also used to treat other conditions such as congestive heart failure, which can impair blood circulation throughout the body. Sometimes, when there is too much fluid in the body, it can cause swelling, a condition called edema, so diuretics can help reduce this swelling (Bartoli et al., 2017; Bobkova et al., 2016; Khan et al., 2019).

All diuretics promote the excretion of water from the body, primarily through the kidneys. The kidneys filter blood, remove waste products, regulate the body's fluid balance, and maintain electrolyte levels (Mathew, 2011). Diuretics are also used by people with chronic kidney disease to treat edema, lower blood pressure, and manage high potassium levels (hyperkalemia) in the blood. In healthy individuals, mild diuresis may occur with increased water intake. These drugs allow the body to remove extra water through more urine. The balance of electrolytes in the blood is closely connected to fluid balance (Johnson et al., 2015).

If diabetes is not controlled, too much glucose (sugar) stays in the bloodstream. When this glucose reaches the kidneys for filtering, it can stop the body from reabsorbing water, which causes more urine to be made. Diabetes can also make someone feel very thirsty, which might cause them to drink more. Another cause of diuresis is exposure to cold temperatures which could abnormally increase their urine (Ntchapda, 2015).

Agoho, which is also known as *Casuarina equisetifolia* Linn., grows in many parts of Southeast Asia, the Pacific, and other coastal areas with warm climates. It is a large, evergreen tree that can grow up to 20 meters tall. Its bark is brown and rough. It has unisexual flowers, slender spikes, and ellipsoid cones. The plant can be found all over the Philippines along sandy seashores, and also in open sandy valleys near streams. People grow it to help prevent soil erosion and protect the environment. Some Agoho trees can be found in other roads in the Philippines, but they have been disfigured by pruning and do not exhibit their usual elegant shape. This fast-growing and drought tolerant native tree is great for soil fertility or nitrogen fixation. This plant is also used in traditional medicine, especially in Asia, where people have used its bark in decoctions to treat problems like stomach issues, kidney problems, and heart-related conditions, as well as produce antidiarrheal, antifungal, antibacterial, and nephroprotective effects (Barua et al., 2015; El-Tantawy et al., 2013; Hossen et al., 2014; Muhammad et al., 2009; Muthuraj et al., 2019; Rao and Eswaraiah, 2018; Shafiq et al., 2012; Uy & Garcia, 2015). These findings support the current study, which aims to further investigate how Agoho bark extract can help the body get rid of extra fluids in animal tests. Even though it has many uses, there is not much scientific research on how Agoho works effectively as a diuretic.

The study on Agoho's diuretic effects is essential to confirm their traditional claims and to find some natural alternatives to medicines like furosemide. Saranya and Gowrie (2016) did some early work showing its efficacy, but more studies are needed to understand pharmacological properties and safety in controlled experimental models. This study determines if the ethanol and water extracts from Agoho bark work as a diuretic in Sprague-Dawley rats.

Objectives

The primary objectives of this study are to evaluate whether Agoho bark decoction have diuretic potential in rats and to identify phytochemicals present in its extract.

1. Evaluate the percentage yield of Agoho (*Casuarina equisetifolia*) bark extract.
2. Determine the biologic activity of Agoho bark extract on rats.
3. Identify the diuretic activity of Agoho bark on male Sprague-Dawley rats.

Hypothesis

Ho: There is no significant difference between pre-inducement and post- inducement urine level for each treatment. Both ethanolic and aqueous extracts do not have a potential diuretic effect.

Ho: There is no significant difference between furosemide as positive control, as well as ethanolic and aqueous extracts. Agoho (extracted with ethanol or water) cannot be a potential substitute to furosemide as positive control.

Scope and Limitation

This study limits its coverage on the method of extraction of Agoho bark and its potential diuretic effect on male Sprague Dawley rats. While the study only focuses on the bark of the plant, the study also excludes histopathological examinations and is conducted merely on observations, as well as the identification and determination of the diuretic efficacy of the plant extract. This was done and executed through the collection, authentication, and preparation of the plant material. The extraction of Agoho is limited with the respective use of ethanol and water. Furosemide was utilized as positive control in the study. No other standard drug with diuretic effect was compared to Agoho in this study. Saline solution was used as negative control in the study. Male Sprague-Dawley rats were utilized in the experiment to get the volume of urine treated per group. The findings are intended to guide further pharmacological exploration of Agoho.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used an experimental research design to assess the diuretic activity of *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Agoho) bark extracts. Both ethanolic and aqueous extracts were prepared and given to male Sprague-Dawley rats. The rats' responses were compared against a positive control (furosemide) and a negative control (saline solution). The design enabled a direct comparison of the extracts' diuretic effects with a known standard.

The diuretic effects of *Casuarina equisetifolia* bark ethanolic extracts were investigated in male Sprague-Dawley rats. The ethanolic extracts at various doses were administered to the rats. Urine volumes were measured in 3-hour variations after administration of the extract. The experiments were done under similar conditions, using a synthetic drug called furosemide as a reference for comparison. Urinary concentrations of sodium and potassium ions were revealed with flame photometry, while chloride ion was determined titrimetrically (Aher, 2010).

Collection and Authentication of Plant Material

Fresh Agoho bark samples were collected from Romblon Province, Municipality of San Fernando, Barangay Panangcalan, Philippines. The samples were cleaned, shade-dried, and ground finely using a mechanical grinder and passed through a sieve. The plant material was authenticated at the University of the Philippines, Los Baños, confirming it as *Casuarina equisetifolia* Linn.

Extraction Procedures

The powdered bark underwent cold maceration for three days and filtered the extract into another flask using a filter paper for phytochemical screening. For the ethanolic extract, the bark was ground into powder and soaked in 95% ethanol in a 1:10 ratio by weight to volume for 72 hours, while being stirred continuously. After soaking, the mixture was filtered and then heated gently under low pressure using a rotary evaporator to remove the liquid. The remaining substance was then dried to form a semi-solid material. For the aqueous extract, the same powdered bark was soaked in distilled water in a 1:10 ratio for 72 hours with occasional stirring. The extract was filtered and lyophilized to obtain a powdered residue.

Extraction Yield

The number of active substances extracted from the Agoho bark was calculated using a specific formula.

$$\text{Percentage yield} = \frac{\text{Actual volume}}{\text{Theoretical volume}} \times 100\%$$

Using the formula shown, the actual yield is 14.2 g divided by theoretical yield which is 545.0 g multiplied by 100% is equal to 2.6%. The crude extraction of dried 545.0 g Agoho Bark produced 2.4 L ethanolic extract and the concentration of the filtrate yielded 14.2 g (2.6%) of semi-solid extract.

Phytochemical Screening

Table 1. Phytochemical Screening

Constituents	Test	Theoretical Result (+)
Carbohydrates	Molisch Test	Purple ring at the junction
	Fehling's Test	Brick red precipitate
	Osazone Test	Formation of crystals
	Seliwanoff's Test for Ketoses	Cherry red solution
	Bial's Orcinol Test	Pentoses: blue or green Hexoses: Muddy brown Methyl pentose / ketohexose: Orange or olive-green solution
	Keller-Killiani Test	Reddish brown ring
Glycosides	Guignard Test	Various shades of red
Saponins	Sodium Bicarbonate Test	Formation of a stable and dense froth
Sterols	Salkowski Test	Formation of red bicholestadien disulfonate Bluish color between the chloroform and sulfuric acid layer
	Liebermann-Burchard Test	Deep green color
Tannins	Ferric C Test	Green: hydrolyzable tannins Blue: non-hydrolyzable tannins
Flavonins	Borntrager's Test	Pink color
Alkaloids	Mayer's Test	White to cream precipitate
	Valser's Test	Reddish brown precipitate
	Wagner's Test	Reddish brown precipitate

Table 1 identifies the phytochemical screening. Qualitative phytochemical tests were conducted on both ethanolic and aqueous extracts to detect bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, sterols, glycosides, and triterpenes. Standard methods were used (Evans et al., 2009; Shah & Seth, 2020). The amount of each compound was noted as trace (+), moderate (++), or abundant (+++).

Selection of Test Animal

Healthy male Sprague-Dawley rats, weighing between 160 and 200 grams, were obtained from a certified supplier. The animals were kept in a standard lab environment with a temperature of 25 ± 2 °C, humidity between 60–70%, and a 12-hour light/dark cycle. They were allowed to be acclimatized for one week before the tests began. Rats were given regular food and water freely available at all times. All procedures were done following guidelines for the proper care and use of laboratory animals.

Screening and Induction of Diuretics/Treatment of Animal with Agoho Extract

A total of 16 rats were randomly divided into four groups (n=4 per group):

Group I (Positive Control): Furosemide (1 mg/kg, intraperitoneal injection).

Group II (Negative Control): Normal saline solution (25 ml/kg, orally).

Group III (Ethanollic Extract): Ethanollic extract of Agoho bark (100 mg/kg, oral gavage).

Group IV (Aqueous Extract): Aqueous extract of Agoho bark (100 mg/kg, oral gavage).

The rats were fasted overnight and deprived of water for 18 hours before dosing. Following treatment, each rat was placed in a metabolic cage to separate urine and feces. Urine was collected over a 3-hour period.

Measurement of Effectivity

Parameters such as body weight before and after test period, as well as the total concentration of sodium (Na⁺), potassium (K⁺) and chlorine (Cl⁻) in the urine of individual rat was measured and recorded. Flame photometry was used to measure Na⁺ and K⁺ levels. For Cl⁻ concentration, a titration test with silver nitrate solution (N/50) was performed, using three drops of a 5% potassium chromate solution as the indicator. The volume of urine of each rat was measured before and after administration of normal saline, furosemide, ethanollic and aqueous extract. The increase in the volume of urine after administration were observed.

Data Analysis

The results are shown as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). A statistical test called one-way ANOVA was used, followed by Tukey's post-hoc test to compare differences between the groups. A p-value lower than 0.05 was considered to show a significant difference.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Phytochemical Test for Plant Constituents of Agoho Bark extract

Chemical Constituents	Ethanol Extract
Sterols	+++
Triterpenes	++
Flavonoids	+++
Alkaloids	+++
Saponins	+
Glycosides	++
Tannins	+++

Legend: (+) Traces, (++) Moderate, (+++) Abundant

Table 2 shows the result of the qualitative phytochemical screening of the ethanollic crude extract of the leaves of the Agoho bark. Flavonoids, alkaloids, and tannins were found abundant (+++), while triterpenes and glycosides were present in moderate amounts (++), and saponins were found in small traces (+). The chemical components of the ethanollic extract from *Casuarina equisetifolia* Linn. are all positive.

Table 3. Average Body Weight (in grams), Urine Baseline, and Post-Inducement Urine Level (in ml)

Treatment	Body Weight	Urine Baseline	Post Inducement
Positive Control (furosemide)	177.24	1.22	7.92
Negative Control (Saline Solution)	179.69	1.24	3.78
Ethanollic Extract	181.14	1.25	6.47
Aqueous Extract	167.80	1.16	3.78

Table 3 shows the average body weight of rats, baseline urine levels, and post-inducement urine volumes after being given different treatments: positive control (Furosemide), negative control, ethanolic extract, and aqueous extract. The average body weights were very similar in all groups: positive control (177.24 g), negative control (179.69 g), ethanolic extract (181.14 g), and aqueous extract (167.80 g). These numbers show that the rats in each group have similar size, which means body weight probably did not affect the results of the urine tests.

Baseline urine levels were also very close across all groups, ranging from 1.16 ml (aqueous extract) to 1.25 ml (ethanolic extract). These small differences mean the rats started the experiment with similar levels of hydration and urine output, making it easier to compare the results after treatment.

After the diuretic treatments were given, all groups had higher urine output. The positive control group, which got Furosemide, had the most urine at 7.92 ml. The ethanolic extract group had 6.47 ml, and the aqueous extract group had 4.88 ml. The negative control group, which did not have any diuretic effects, had only 3.78 ml of urine on average. These results suggest that both the ethanol and water extracts of Agoho have some diuretic effects.

Table 4. Test for Significant Difference in Body Weight per Treatment

Control	Compared Treatment	P-value	Significance
Positive Control	Negative Control	.847	Not Significant
	Ethanolic Extract	.760	Not Significant
	Aqueous Extract	.463	Not Significant
Ethanolic Extract		.910	Not Significant
Negative Control	Aqueous Extract	.358	Not Significant
Ethanolic Extract	Aqueous Extract	.305	Not Significant

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

A statistical test determined if there were any significant differences in body weight across treatment groups (Table 4). It shows that the p-values were higher than 0.05, which means there were no significant difference in body weight across groups. This shows that the animals were similar in their physical condition at the baseline of the study. Any changes in urine output probably were not observed because of differences in weight, thereby not affecting the results of the treatment.

Table 5. Test for Significant Difference in Urine Level Before Inducement

Control	Compared Treatment	P-value	Significance
Positive Control	Negative Control	.844	Not Significant
	Ethanolic Extract	.757	Not Significant
	Aqueous Extract	.469	Not Significant
Ethanolic Extract		.910	Not Significant
Negative Control	Aqueous Extract	.361	Not Significant
Ethanolic Extract	Aqueous Extract	.308	Not Significant

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

Table 5 shows the results of a statistical test for differences in urine levels prior to inducement. P-values were higher than 0.05, meaning there were no significant differences among the baseline urine outputs in different groups. This confirms that all groups had similar urine levels, which ensures that any changes after treatment are valid and reliable.

Table 6. Test for Significant Difference in Urine Level for Post-Inducement (Within Treatments)

Treatment	p-value	Significance
Positive Control	.001	Significant
Ethanollic Extract	.000	Significant
Aqueous Extract	.001	Significant

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

Table 6 shows the test for significant difference in urine level for post-inducement (within treatments). Post-inducement changes in urine volume in each group were determined to see if they were statistically significant. Results showed that all three groups—positive control, ethanolic extract, and aqueous extract—had significant increases in urine volume ($p < 0.05$ for all). For the positive control group, urine output went up from 1.22 ml to 7.92 ml after giving Furosemide, which confirms its known diuretic effect. In the ethanolic extract group, urine volume rose significantly to 6.47 ml, showing that the ethanol-based Agoho extract has diuretic properties. The aqueous extract group also showed a significant increase, reaching 4.88 ml, proving that the water-based Agoho extract also has diuretic effects. These results show that both types of Agoho extract can increase urine production in animals, suggesting effectiveness as natural diuretics in medicine.

Table 7. Test for Significant Difference in Urine Level Between Treatments (Between Groups)

Control	Compared Treatment	P-value	Significance
Positive Control	Ethanollic Extract	.007	Significant
	Aqueous Extract	.000	Significant
Ethanollic Extract	Aqueous Extract	.004	Significant

**Significant at .05 alpha level*

Table 7 shows the test for significant difference in urine level for across treatments (Between Groups). A comparison of post-inducement urine levels showed statistically significant differences across different groups ($p < 0.05$). The positive control group significantly made more urine than both ethanolic and aqueous extracts, showing that Furosemide remains the strongest at increasing urine production. Both types of Agoho extracts had some diuretic effect, but neither worked as well as the standard medicine. Between these two Agoho extracts, ethanolic extracts caused more urine than aqueous extracts (6.47 ml vs. 4.88 ml), suggesting that alcohol might be an effective solvent extracting the active parts of the plant that help increase urine.

It was also observed that sodium (Na⁺) significantly increased in both ethanolic and aqueous extract groups compared to the negative control ($p < 0.05$). Potassium (K⁺) moderately increased with ethanolic extract, less with aqueous extract. Chloride's (Cl⁻) higher excretion was observed in the ethanolic extract compared to the aqueous extract, though still lower than furosemide. Furosemide was significantly more effective than both ethanolic and aqueous extracts ($p < 0.05$). Ethanolic extract showed significantly higher diuretic activity compared to aqueous extract ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Furosemide is known to increase urine production, showing its diuretic effect. Agoho, when extracted using ethanol or water, shows a possible diuretic effect. However, ethanol extract is more effective than the water extract in increasing urine production. The ethanolic extract demonstrated strong diuretic activity, significantly greater than the aqueous extract. Both ethanolic and aqueous extracts showed that Agoho can help increase urine production; however, they were not as effective as furosemide.

Based on the results, the succeeding statements are recommended for further enhancement.

1. More research is needed for other medicinal effects of Agoho bark or the plant as a whole.
2. Clinical trials should be conducted to evaluate the plant's effects for future use and treatment.
3. Other parts of the tree can be studied for additional medicinal benefits.
4. Different dosages and forms of the drug should be developed.
5. More studies should be done on using the bark for other conditions such as cancer.
6. Further tests on different concentrations of Agoho may be conducted rather than just ethanol and water extracts.

References

- Aher, A. N., Pal, S. C., Yadav, S. K., Patil, U. K., & Bhattacharya, S. (2010). Isolation and characterization of phytoconstituents from *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Casuarinaceae). *Asian Journal of Chemistry*, 22(5), 3429-3434. <https://asianpubs.org/index.php/ajchem/article/view/11565>
- Bartoli, E., Rossi, L., Sola, D., Castello, L., Sainaghi, P. P., & Smirne, C. (2017). Use, misuse and abuse of diuretics. *European Journal of Internal Medicine*, 39, 9-17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejim.2017.01.016>
- Bobkova, I., Chebotareva, N., Kozlovskaya, L., & Shilov, E. (2016). Edema in renal diseases—current view on pathogenesis. *Nephrology @ Point of Care*, 2(1), pocj-5000204. <https://doi.org/10.5301/pocj.500020>
- El-Tantawy, W. H., Mohamed, S. A. H., & Abd Al Haleem, E. N. (2013). Evaluation of biochemical effects of *Casuarina equisetifolia* extract on gentamicin-induced nephrotoxicity and oxidative stress in rats. Phytochemical analysis. *Journal of Clinical Biochemistry and Nutrition*, 53(3), 158-165. <https://doi.org/10.3164/jcfn.13-19>
- Evans, W. C. (2020). *Trease and Evans pharmacognosy* (17th ed.). Saunders Ltd.
- Hossen, S. M., Jahidul Islam, J. I., Hossain, S. S., Rahman, M. M., & Firoj Ahmed, F. A. (2014). Phytochemical and biological evaluation of MeOH extract of *Casuarina equisetifolia* (Linn.) leaves. *European Journal of Medicinal Plants*, 4(8), 927-936. <https://doi.org/10.9734/EJMP/2014/9820>
- Johnson, E. C., Muñoz, C. X., Le Bellego, L., Klein, A., Casa, D. J., Maresh, C. M., & Armstrong, L. E. (2015). Markers of the hydration process during fluid volume modification in women with habitual high or low daily fluid intakes. *European Journal of Applied Physiology*, 115(5), 1067-1074. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-014-3088-2>
- Khan, Y. H., Sarriff, A., Adnan, A. S., Khan, A. H., & Mallhi, T. H. (2016). Chronic kidney disease, fluid overload and diuretics: a complicated triangle. *PloS One*, 11(7), e0159335. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0159335>
- Mathew, G. E., Mathew, B., Shaneeb, M. M., & Nyanthara, B. (2011). Diuretic activity of leaves of *Garcinia cambogia* in rats. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 73(2), 228-230. <https://www.ijpsonline.com/articles/diuretic-activity-of-leaves-of-garcinia-cambogia-in-rats.html>

- Muhammad, H. L., Garba, R., Abdullah, A. S., Adefolalu, F. S., Busari, M. B., Hamzah, R. U., & Makun, H. A. (2022). Hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic properties of *Casuarina equisetifolia* leaf extracts in alloxan induced diabetic rats. *Pharmacological Research-Modern Chinese Medicine*, 2, 100034. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prmcm.2021.100034>
- Muthuraj, S., Muthusamy, P., Radha, R., & Ilango, K. (2019). Pharmacognostical, phytochemical and pharmacological review on *Casuarina equisetifolia* Linn. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 8(4), 328-339. https://wjpr.s3.ap-south-1.amazonaws.com/article_issue/1556706470.pdf
- Ntchapda, F., Kakesse, M., Fokam, M. A. T., Pancha, O. M., Abakar, D., & Dimo, T. (2015). Evaluation of the diuretic effects of crude stem bark extraction of *Zanthoxylum heitzii* (Rutaceae) in Wistar rats. *Journal of Integrative Medicine*, 13(5), 326-335. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-4964\(15\)60188-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-4964(15)60188-1)
- Saranya, V., & Gowrie, S. U. (2016). Green synthesis, optimization, characterization of silver nanoparticles using *Casuarina equisetifolia* bark extract and its assays. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 6(3), 797-814. https://wjpr.s3.ap-south-1.amazonaws.com/article_issue/1488272882.pdf
- Rao, O. U., & Eswaraiah, M. C. (2018). Single dose oral toxicity study of ethanolic extract from inflorescence of *Casuarina equisetifolia* in Wistar rats. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 8, 44-47. <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/full/10.5555/20203459450>
- Shafiq, Y., Naqvi, B. S., Rizwani, G. H., Usman, M., Shah, B. A., & Hina, B. (2014). Anti-acne activity of *Casuarina equisetifolia* bark extract: A randomized clinical trial. *Bangladesh Journal of Pharmacology*, 9(3), 337-341. <https://www.bdpsjournal.org/index.php/bjp/article/view/237>
- Shah, B., & Seth, A. K., (2020). *Textbook of pharmacognosy and phytochemistry* (2nd ed.). CBS Publishers and Distributors Pvt Ltd.
- Uy, M. M., & Garcia, K. I. (2015). Evaluation of the antioxidant properties of the leaf extracts of Philippine medicinal plants *Casuarina equisetifolia* Linn, *Cyperus brevifolius* (Rottb) Hassk, *Drymoglossum piloselloides* Linn, *Ixora chinensis* Lam, and *Piper abbreviatum* Opiz. *Advances in Agriculture & Botanics*, 7(2), 71-79. <https://aab.bioflux.com.ro/docs/2015.71-79.pdf>